

Assessment of GHG Emission Reduction Due to Upgrade of Big-Scale WWTPs in Ukraine

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Abstract

Reduction of GHG emissions from WWTPs can contribute to achieving carbon neutrality in Ukraine. However, there is still a lack of high-resolution and time-series GHG emission inventories for WWTPs in Ukraine. In this study, we develop an emission inventory of WWTPs (facility-scale) for N₂O and CO₂ emissions from the biggest WWTPs. Calculations of GHG emissions from existing wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in the biggest Ukrainian cities (Kharkiv, Kyiv, Lviv), where the aerobic biological process is used for treatment, have been carried out for business-as-usual alternative and in cases of A/O and A₂/O processes introduction. The impact of the main economically feasible technologies for biological wastewater treatment from nutrients and sludge processing to the nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide generation at facilities has been calculated.

Keywords

A/O and A₂/O process, biological wastewater treatment; greenhouse gas emissions; wastewater treatment plant upgrade.

INTRODUCTION

Municipal wastewater treatment facilities are essential for managing wastewater pollution. Historically, efforts to improve wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) have focused on achieving high effluent quality (*Zhang Q. et al., 2016*). However, while reducing water pollution, these facilities also present environmental risks, particularly through greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

In recent years, attention has shifted toward ensuring the sustainability of WWTPs by balancing economic efficiency and environmental impact. A critical factor influencing their performance is GHG emissions, as WWTPs are significant sources of anthropogenic emissions, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), released during biological treatment and sludge processing (*Kumar A. et al., 2021*). Additionally, indirect CO₂ emissions arise from energy consumption for plant operation (*Gu Y. et al., 2016*).

Although the IPCC (*IPCC, 2019*) considers the CO₂ emissions from biological processes to be biogenic and excludes them from national emission inventories, recent studies have shown that a significant fraction of CO₂ emissions from WWTPs may originate from fossil sources (*Schneider A.G. et al. 2015*). Neglecting these emissions could underestimate WWTPs' environmental impact. While WWTPs contribute a small share of global emissions, accurately estimating and mitigating them is vital for countries pursuing carbon neutrality.

In 2024, Ukraine made a significant step in addressing GHG emissions by restoring inventory processes and an annual emissions registry. This is particularly relevant for municipal WWTPs, which significantly influence the country's carbon balance.

Ukrainian WWTPs, unlike most European ones, use outdated treatment technologies, such as aeration without denitrification or other methods without the use of air, in 99% of cases. Furthermore, elevated concentrations of pollutants in treated wastewater can lead to the release of greenhouse gases when discharged into natural water bodies. These emissions are often overlooked due to insufficient data

on the quality of receiving waters and downstream discharge pathways. That's why the calculation of GHG emissions from the largest Ukrainian plants (with capacities of more or about 100 000 cubic meters per day) is crucial for understanding their national impact.

With Ukraine's ongoing large-scale WWTP reconstructions, evaluating the impact of upgrades on GHG emissions is essential. These assessments will guide effective mitigation strategies, support low-emission technologies, and help Ukraine meet its climate goals.

The objective of the research is to assess CO₂ and N₂O emissions from big-scale WWTPs during their upgrade in Ukraine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The current operational conditions of large-scale WWTPs (98,000–350,000 m³ per day) in Kyiv, Kharkiv, and Lviv were analyzed in this study (Table 1). GHGs are generated and emitted to atmosphere due to biological treatment processes and discharge of effluents into rivers. Upgrade of big-scale WWTPs will lead to better treatment of waste waters as well as reduction of GHG emissions. There are three main GHGs: CO₂, N₂O and CH₄. Calculations for CO₂ and N₂O emissions associated with municipal wastewater treatment and discharge were made for three alternatives. CH₄ emissions were not calculated due to the lack of data on sludge treatment and disposal processes at treatment plants and the almost complete lack of use of sludge digestion at plants. The calculations used emission factors from IPCC 2019 (IPCC, 2019; Wang et.al, 2022). N₂O and CO₂ emissions were presented in CO₂ equivalents using global warming potential values: 265 and 1, respectively.

Calculations of GHG emissions from WWTPs were performed using the formulas:

$$N_2O_{bio,i} = EF_{bio,N_2O,j} * TN_{in,i} * 265 \quad (1)$$

$$CO_{2bio,i} = EF_{bio,CO_2,j} * COD_{removed,i} \quad (2)$$

Table 1. Influent and effluent wastewater concentrations at WWTPs in Ukrainian cities

City	Kharkiv WWTP-2		Lviv WWTP-1		Lviv WWTP-2		Kyiv WWTP-2 (only 3rd line)	
Flow, m ³ /day	225 000		98 000		215 000		350 000	
Parameters, mg/l	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent
COD	420	60	850	130	430	60	520	60
TN	50	33,5	54	29	45	23	40	30

Where, $N_2O_{bio,i}$ and $CO_{2bio,i}$ refer to N₂O, and CO₂ emissions (g CO₂eq/year) from biological treatment processes in the i^{th} WWTP. $EF_{bio,N_2O,j}$ (g N₂O/kg TN influent) and $EF_{bio,CO_2,j}$ (g CO₂/kg COD removed) are GHG emission factors of the process j in the i^{th} WWTP. $TN_{in,i}$ is the annually influent TN mass (kg TN influent/year) in the i^{th} WWTP, and $COD_{removed,i}$ is the annually removed COD (kg COD removed/year) in the i^{th} WWTP.

Calculations of GHG emissions from the discharge of treated wastewater were performed using the formulas (Wang et.al, 2022):

$$N_2O_{eff,i} = EF_{eff,N_2O,j} * TN_{out,i} * 265 \quad (3)$$

$$CO_{2eff,i} = EF_{eff,CO_2,j} * COD_{out,i} \quad (4)$$

where, $N_2O_{eff,i}$ and $CO_{2eff,i}$ are N₂O and CO₂ emissions (g CO₂eq/year) from the discharge pathway j in the i^{th} WWTP. $EF_{eff,N_2O,j}$ (g N₂O/kg TN effluent) and $EF_{eff,CO_2,j}$ (g CO₂/kg COD effluent) are

effluent emission factors of the discharge pathway j of the i^{th} WWTP. $\text{COD}_{out, i}$ (kg COD effluent/year) and $\text{TN}_{out, i}$ (kg TN effluent/year) are annually effluent COD and TN mass of the i^{th} WWTP.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wastewater treatment facilities in Ukraine need to be upgraded as in most cases aeration tanks (aerobic biological treatment technology) in Ukrainian WWTPs were built in the 1950s-1980s. The technology uses a large amount of air and electricity and does not provide deep removal of nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus) in special anoxic/anaerobic zones, but only COD/BOD removal and partial nitrification.

Data on COD and TN concentrations in wastewater entering the treatment plants of Kyiv, Kharkiv, and Lviv, as well as the residual concentrations of these substances in treated effluent discharged into the Dnipro, Udy, and Poltva rivers, are presented in Table 1. It is important to note that the sections of these rivers receiving the treated wastewater are eutrophic.

From Table 1 data, wastewater treatment provides a sufficiently deep removal of organic substances (COD) by an average of 86.2%, which, compared with the requirements of Directive 91/271/EEC (minimum 75% reduction), fully satisfies existing European standards. The efficiency of TN removal is much lower - it does not exceed 48.9%, and on average is 38.3, which according to Directive 91/271/EEC (minimum 70-80% reduction) is a low-efficiency treatment process (*European Commission, 1991*). Wastewater with high concentrations of nitrogen and phosphorus is discharged into eutrophic rivers, which leads to an increase in GHG emissions.

The implementation of best available treatment technologies - BATT, which include denitrification and biological phosphorus removal processes, will not only significantly reduce GHG emissions during treatment and discharge, but will also require less electricity, which will indirectly reduce the carbon footprint.

Proven and widespread process schemes of biological treatment A/O and A²/O are considered in this work. The effectiveness of applying these technologies in the studied WWTPs will allow achieving regulatory discharges and treatment efficiencies according to Directive 91/271/EEC (*European Commission, 1991*). The difference between A/O and A²/O is that the A²/O process needs an additional pump to provide nitrate recycling, which, although it improves nitrogen removal efficiency, adds carbon emissions during treatment. Accordingly, this difference is taken into account under GHG emissions calculation. The results of calculations of the impact of A/O and A²/O processes on GHG emissions when implemented at the studied WWTPs are presented at Fig. 1.

According to the data in Fig. 1, the implementation of A/O and A²/O processes reduces both CO₂ and N₂O emissions at the studied WWTPs compared to the current traditional Aerobic Biological Treatment technology. CO₂ emissions can be especially reduced effectively under both processes (reduction from 30 to 40%), but A/O is more suitable for implementation. The same trend was observed for N₂O reduction (8-19%) with higher results using A/O process.

Figure 1. Reduction of gas emissions depending on the wastewater treatment process.

Thus, the evaluated WWTP configurations (A/O, A2/O) can be identified as promising strategies for the modernization of Ukrainian treatment facilities within the framework of post-war reconstruction, with the potential to mitigate their operational contribution to the global warming potential and to enhance pathways toward sustainable urban development.

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